

HIERARCHICAL STRUCTURE AND MECHANICAL PROPERTIES OF BAMBOO FIBRILS

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SUMMARY

Bamboo is a rich source of renewable cellulose. It has many outstanding specific properties such as good mechanical properties, bacterial resistant properties etc. Bamboo fibrils are the structural building block of bamboos. Understanding of the structure and the properties of the fibrils at various structural levels will not only shed light on nature's secret of efficient design of structural composites but also inspires creativities. In this paper, bamboo cellulose fibril at different structural levels including bamboo fibre assembly, single bamboo fibre, macrofibril, micro and nanofibril are chemically extracted step by step. The hierarchical structures and the dimensions of these fibrils were examined using SEM and TEM. Different kinds of binding structures of bamboo fibrils were observed. Due to the different resolution and dimensional requirements the mechanical properties of those fibrillar structures were characterized using different testing methods.

Keywords: *Bamboo, Cellulosic fibril, hierarchical structure, mechanical properties*

1. INTRODUCTION

Cellulosic material has obtained more and more attention (.) in the recent years because of their renewable nature and all around properties. Many interests have been devoted to seeking and producing new cellulosic materials and cellulosic products. Bamboo is one of those favorite cellulose fibril resources abundantly available. With its shorter maturity cycle and high content of cellulose[1, 2], bamboo shows a high potential as sustainable structural material [2-6] as well as textile material[7, 8]. In order to exploit fully the outstanding properties of bamboo, and learning from nature's design strategy a systematical investigation of its hierarchical structure and the corresponding mechanical properties of bamboo fibrils at each hierarchical level are necessary.

Differing from wood, bamboo has no rings in its culm. There are vascular bundles together with the bundle sheaths surrounding the bundles playing the same role as reinforce fibres in composite materials. It is noted that these fibres (both the vascular bundles and the sheaths) are distributed densely in the outer region and sparsely in the inner region[2], as shown in Figure 1. Like most of lignocellulosic fibres, those fibres are built hierarchically from nano to micro fibrils which further build up macro bamboo fibres, Figure 2.

Fig.1 Structure of bamboo culm. a) a piece of bamboo culm; b) vascular bundle.

Fig.2 Hierarchical structure of cellulosic fibre (Frey-Wyssling and Mühlethaler, 1965).

In this paper, bamboo fibre bundles, single bamboo fibres, macro and micro fibrils, and nanofibrils were successively extracted from bamboo culm by chemical processes. The structure of these fibrils was investigated and the mechanical properties were measured.

2. EXPERIMENT

A piece of dried Chinese meso bamboo culm was used. Sodium hydroxide, potassium hydroxide, hydrochloric acid (10N), sodium hypochlorite(5%) and sulfuric acid (95~98%) were purchased from Thermo Fisher Scientific Inc. Anthraquinone was purchased from Sigma-Aldrich Co.

A piece of bamboo culm was observed and then fibrils at different hierarchical levels were extracted from the culm step by step. All the fibrils except nanofibrils were observed using SEM. Due to its nano scale, nanofibrils were observed using AFM. In order to provide evidence of the presence of nanocrystal, electron diffractions were conducted on these nanofibrils.

2.1 Extraction of bamboo fibre fibrils

All the extraction processes were carried out based on the procedure established by Wan et al.[9,10]. Bamboo culm was cut into small pieces (1X5 cm), and soaked in 17.5wt% sodium hydroxide aqueous solution with 0.1wt% anthraquinone as additives at 50~70°C for 2 hours, subsequently the temperature was increased to 120 °C for 2~3hours. The softened pieces were grind into separate fibre bundles and washed with distilled water.

The washed fibre bundles were subsequently soaked in 1M hydrochloric acid solution at 60~80 °C for 2 hours, 5wt% potassium hydroxide aqueous solution at 80 °C for 2 hours, 1M hydrochloric acid solution at 60~80 °C for 2 hours. Followed each process, the samples were wash with distilled water. The above process was repeated for 1~3 times depending on the conditions of the separated bamboo fibres. The separated bamboo fibrils were then bleached with 1.05wt% sodium hypochlorite solution for 30min followed by washing with distilled water. The samples were finally soaked in 1wt% sulfuric acid solution for 20min and washed with fluent distilled water.

The hydrolysis process was based on method established by Dong et al. [11-13]. The separated fibres were stored in a freezer for at least 12 hours. 60wt% sulfuric acid was poured onto sample and slowly stirred for 10~20 minutes at ambient temperature. The solution was 10-fold diluted and stored in freezer for at least 4h, centrifuged and washed.

The process for obtaining nanofibrils was essentially the same as the process for extracting macro and microfibrils. The differences are the concentration of sulfuric acid and the time for hydrolysis. The concentration of sulfuric acid was changed to 65wt% and the time was 45~60 minutes.

2.2 Measurement of Mechanical properties

Considering their size scale and the corresponding load bearing capacity, the mechanical properties of the various structural entities were measured using instruments with appropriate sensitivities. The equipments include KES tensile tester, micro tensile tester, nanoindenter and Atomic Force Microscope (AFM). The sensitivity of each equipment are shown in Table 1.

Table 1 size scale of bamboo fibrils and sensitivities of according equipments

Sample			Equipment	
Type	Diameter	Length	Sensitivity	Type
Fibre bundle	50-210um	4-5cm	0.1g	KES-G1
Single fibre	3-27um	<5mm	0.01g	Micro-tester
	3-27um	<5mm	1uN-10N	Nanoindenter
Nanofibril	11-25nm	>230nm	1pN-uN	AFM

The fibre bundles were dried in an oven at 70°C for about 24 hours and cooled down before testing using the KES-G1 Tensile Tester (Kato-Tech Co. Ltd.). The samples were tested at gauge length of 10mm, 20mm and 30mm.

Single bamboo fibres were tested using a micro-tensile tester (custom built at Paprican).

The testing length was 1mm. To check the effects of the chemical processes on bamboo fibres, a nanoindentation system (Nano Indenter XP System, MTS Nano Instruments, OakRidge, TN, USA) was used to measure the elastic modulus of bamboo fibre directly from the bamboo matrix. The measurement was carried on with a Berkovich diamond tip (AccuTip™) under continuous stiffness measurement mode (CSM). Indenter tip calibration was conducted before indentation testing. The displacement was controlled at a depth of 3000nm. The elastic modulus between the indentation depths of 1000 and 3000 nm were averaged and used for data analysis. The Poisson's ratio was set to be 0.38, and allowable drift rate was set at 0.5 nm/s.

The Atomic Force Microscopy (AFM) was used to measure the mechanical properties of nanofibrils, as shown in Figure 3. To prepare the specimen, a dope of nanofibril suspension was drop on a glass slide and dried in air. The fibrils were first imaged. For the measurement, the AFM tip was then positioned on top of the points of interest and then was approached to sample surface. The force on the specimen is generated from the deflection of the cantilever. The amount of indentation/deformation z can be obtained from the difference of the height of tip and the end of the cantilever. A silicon carbide tip of 20 nm and elastic modulus of 130 GPa were used. Three different measurements were made on three different locations.

Fig. 3 Schematic diagram of AFM test

3. HIERARCHICAL STRUCTURE OF BAMBOO FIBRILS

After the chemical process, fibre bundles, single fibres, macro and microfibrils, nanofibrils aggregates, nanofibrils were obtained. The hierarchical structures of bamboo was observed as shown in Fig.4.

Fig.4 Bamboo fibrils and the hierarchical structures. a) fibre bundles. b) single fibres. c) macro and microfibrils. d) microfibrils aggregates. e) microfibrils. f) a single bamboo fibre with broken tip. g) hemicellulose and lignin composed membrane out layers of single bamboo fibre. h) a broken fibre shows the inner fibrils and the outer layers. i) binding structure of macrofibril. j) microfibrils wrapped on the surface of a macrofibril .

From the SEM pictures (Fig. 4(a)), it can be seen that the single bamboo fibres with sharp tips are mostly well aligned in bundles. At the macro and micro fibril scale, however, the structure becomes complex. As shown in Fig.4 (f)-(h) the macrofibril bundles are surrounded by membrane layers composed of hemicellulose and lignin. Twining macrofibrils (as shown in Fig.4 (i)) are also present in macro-scaled bundles as binders. Fig. 4(j) shows the microfibrils are aligned at angles between 10 and 20 degree to the axis of the macrofibril form macrofibrils, Nanofibril aggregates are formed by overlapped single microfibrils which, like single bamboo fibres, also have sharp tips. This configuration may partly explain why bamboos are more flexible than wood. During bending the sharp tips are more flexible, be able to provide more freedom of mobility of the crystallites as illustrated in Fig.5.

Fig.5 Schematic diagram of the hierarchical structure of bamboo

Fig.6 shows the distribution of the diameter of the fibrillar structures. The diameter of single fibres are 8~9 μm , whereas the diameter of macrofibrils and microfibrils are between 85 nm and 2.7 μm .

Fig. 6 Diameter distributions of bamboo fibrils. a) Macro and micro fibrils.

b) Single fibre.

To verify the crystal structure, electron diffraction were conducted through TEM on nanocrystal aggregates and nanocrystallites. The presence of small sparks distributed along the bright rings proved the existence of crystal structures, as shown in Fig.(7). As the size of crystalline becomes smaller, the sparkles become fuzzy. This is due to the smaller of the diameter of crystallite is, the less diffraction can be captured.

Fig.7 Electron diffraction. a) nanofibril aggregate. b) nanofibril.

4. MECHANICAL PROPERTIES

The mechanical testing results are shown as in Table.2.

Table 2 Mechanical testing results of bamboo fibrils

Material	Equipment	Strength (MPa)	Strain (%)	Modulus (GPa)
Fibre Bundle	Tensile tester	387	16.7	2.7
Single Fibre	Micro tensile tester	916	12.6	13.6
Single Fibre*	Nanoindenter	N/A	N/A	13
Regenerated Fibre	Tensile tester	290	71.2	1.8
Bamboo Nanofibril	AFM	N/A	N/A	40

Figure 8 shows the force-deformation curves for the fibril specimen and mica measured with AFM. The elastic modulus of the fibre can be evaluated based on these measured parameters using the approach of Kracke and Damaschke[14, 15].

$$dF / d(\Delta z) = (2/\pi^{1/2}) E^* A^{1/2} \quad (1)$$

Where A is the contact area, E* is the effective Young's modulus of the contact as defined by:

$$1/E^* = (1-\nu_1^2)/E_1 + (1-\nu_2^2)/E_2 \quad (2)$$

Here, E₁, E₂ and ν₁ and ν₂ are the elastic modulus and the Poisson's ratios of the sample and the tip.

From Eq.(1), we developed the following relationship

$$E_f^* = \frac{d_f}{d_s} E_s^* \quad (3)$$

Where, *f* and *s* are respectively stand for the tested fibre and specimen used as standard sample, and *d* is the abbreviation of *dF / d(Δz)*

Fig.8 Force vs. indentation. a) mica. b) nanofibrils.

In this experiment, Mica was used as a standard sample. The effective Young's modulus of bamboo nanofiril was obtained through comparing the different values of *d* for nanofibril and mica, since the elastic modulus and Poisson's ratio of mica are known. Using Eq.(2) and (3), the average elastic modulus of bamboo nanofibril were

calculated to be 40 GPa.

As shown in Fig.9 the strength of bamboo fibre bundles is between 183-565MPa with an average elastic modulus of 2.7GPa, Fig.9. It is well known that the tensile properties of fibres are sensitive to gage length. As the gage length increases the strength of the fibres tends to decrease and the failure strain tends to increase.

A great deal of variation was detected in the test results of bamboo single fibres with strength and strain varies, as shown in Fig.9. The strength values range from 1.48GPa, to 516MPa whereas the strain to failure varies from 5.5%-19.5%. This divergence can be attributed to non-uniform diameter of bamboo fibres or the presence of weak points. Similar to nanoindentation measurement result, the average elastic modulus is around 13GPa which is much higher than that of fibre bundles. The reason of the difference between the mechanical properties of fibre bundle and single bamboo fibres is that, as explained above, the strength of bamboo fibres is stronger than the bonding between bamboo fibres and the matrix.

Fig.9 Tensile testing results of bamboo fibrils. a) fibre bundles; b) single fibres.

The AFM testing results showed that nanofibril has higher modulus than single bamboo fibre. This is due to size effect. When the size of the fibre is reduced to the nanoscale, it becomes possible for the fibril to avoid the presence of defects, and the strength will be more likely to reach the theoretical strength of covalent bonds.

5. CONCLUSIONS

This study showed that bamboo fibre has a complex hierarchical composite structure, which makes bamboo strong and tough. Investigation of the mechanical properties of structures at different hierarchical level further confirmed the size effect of the stress strain properties of materials. Specifically it has been demonstrated that nanofibril extracted from cellulosic materials has promising mechanical properties. Coupling with the abundant availability, sustainability, and the outstanding combination of strength and toughness bamboo based cellulosic fibres has potential applications in many fields including building construction, automobile, and aerospace.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

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